

CHEMISTRY OF RARE EARTHS. PART X. UROTROPIN AND
ANTIPYRINE COMPLEXES OF THIOCYANATES AND
DITHIONATES OF RARE EARTHS

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Preparation and properties of complexes of rare earth thiocyanates and dithionates with urotropin and antipyrine have been described.

Rare earth nitrates have been known to give beautiful crystalline compounds with urotropin (Barbieri and Calzolari, *Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1911, v, 20, 164) and antipyrine (Kolbe, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 88, 143). Similar compounds with rare earth perchlorates, iodides and nitrites have been isolated by Wilke-Dorfurt and Schliephake (*ibid.*, 1928, 170, 123) and others. One of the authors (N. K. D.) has isolated several compounds of rare earth thiosulphates with urotropin and antipyrine. Preparation and properties of similar complexes of urotropin and antipyrine with rare earth (La, Ce, Pr) thiocyanates and dithionates form the subject matter of the present communication. Simple rare earth thiocyanates and dithiocyanates have long been known in the solid state as highly soluble and hygroscopic salts. These complexes, however, are of moderate solubility and not hygroscopic, and have been obtained as beautiful shining crystals.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of Rare Earth Salts used as Starting Material: (a) *Lanthanum salt* used as the starting material was double ammonium nitrate, obtained through the courtesy of Société des Produits, Chimique de Terre Rares as a free gift. It was purified by conversion into anhydrous sulphate which was then dissolved in ice-water and heated to 33°, when hydrated lanthanum sulphate (9H₂O, hexagonal) was obtained pure, being not isomorphous with hydrated praseodymium sulphate (8H₂O, monoclinic), the impurity present in it.

(b) *Cerium salt* was extracted from monazite sand by the classical ceric ammonium nitrate method. It was further purified by several recrystallisations of the salt from concentrated nitric acid.

(c) *Praseodymium salt* was obtained from Mss. Frankel and Landau. It is liable to contain little lanthanum. It was purified by fractional crystallisation of the nitrate. Lanthanum accumulated in the solution and pure praseodymium salt precipitated first.

Lanthanum-urotropin Thiocyanate.—Lanthanum nitrate (5 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of water, cooled, and to this was added dropwise urotropin (6 g.), also dissolved in the least quantity of cold water. Separated crystals of lanthanum-urotropin nitrate were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water, added dropwise. The clear solution was then filtered and to the filtrate was then added a saturated solution ammonium thiocyanate containing 5 g. of the solid when the complex salt separated

as beautiful shining microcrystals. These crystals were filtered under suction and washed carefully with ice-cold water.

The compound is white, microcrystalline and moderately soluble in water. It is more soluble in hot water than in the cold. The solution gradually decomposes giving lanthanum hydroxide. It melts at 250° - 55° with decomposition. Its solubility in water at 35° = 15.48 g. in 100 c. c. of the solution. [Found: La, 18.76, 19.01; S, 12.77, 13.18; N, 21.10, 20.88. $\text{La}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires La, 18.86; S, 13.10; N, 20.89 per cent].

Cerous-urotropin thiocyanate was formed when a mixture of cerous nitrate (5 g.) and urotropin (6 g.) was treated with a saturated solution of ammonium thiocyanate.

It resembles the previous salt in all respects, m.p., 255 - 59° (decomp.), solubility at 35° = 11.25 g./100 c. c. [Found: Ce, 18.56, 19.12; S, 13.14, 13.12; N, 20.95, 20.78. $\text{Ce}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ce, 18.97; S, 13.00; N, 20.86 per cent].

Praseodymium-urotropin thiocyanate was also prepared in an analogous way to the other two salts using praseodymium nitrate as the starting material. The compound is light green. In all other respects it resembles the previous compounds. It melts at about 260° with decomposition. Solubility at 35° = 8.67 g./100 c.c. [Found: Pr, 18.88, 19.28; S, 12.88, 13.25; N, 21.21, 20.78. $\text{Pr}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pr, 19.08; S, 13.00; N, 20.84 per cent].

Lanthanum-hexa-antipyrene Thiocyanate.—To a concentrated solution of lanthanum nitrate (3 g.) was added an aqueous solution of antipyrene (5 g.). The crystals separating were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water, added dropwise. To this solution was then added dropwise a saturated solution of ammonium thiocyanate when beautiful colorless crystals separated. It was filtered under suction, washed with ice-cold water twice and dried between folds of filter paper.

The compound is colorless and crystalline in nature, moderately soluble in water but less so than the corresponding urotropin compound. An aqueous solution decomposes on heating. It melts at 270° with decomposition leaving a black residue. Solubility at 35° = 13.67 g./100 c.c. [Found: La, 9.76, 9.58; S, 6.72, 6.75; N, 14.64, 14.71. $\text{La}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires La, 9.64; S, 6.66; N, 14.51 per cent].

Cerous ^m *-hexa-antipyrene thiocyanate* was prepared in the same way as described above substituting cerous nitrate for lanthanum nitrate. It resembles the previous compound in almost all respects. It melts at about 270 - 72° with decomposition; solubility at 35° = 10.52 g./100 c.c. [Found: Ce, 10.01, 9.88; S, 6.78, 6.71; N, 14.54, 14.66. $\text{Ce}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires Ce, 9.77; S, 6.65; N, 14.51 per cent].

Praseodymium-hexa-antipyrene thiocyanate was prepared in an analogous manner using praseodymium nitrate. It is light green in colour. It melts at 274 - 76° leaving a black residue. Solubility at 35° = 7.48 g./100 c.c. [Found: Pr, 9.89, 9.66; S, 6.78, 6.85; N, 14.50, 14.63. $\text{Pr}(\text{SCN})_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires Pr, 9.77; S, 6.65; N, 14.57 per cent].

Lanthanum-urotropin Dithionate.—To a concentrated solution of lanthanum nitrate (5 g.) in cold water was added an aqueous solution of urotropin (10 g.) and the solution was filtered from any precipitate. To this solution was then added a saturated solution

of sodium dithionate dropwise when beautiful white crystals separated which were left for sometime and then filtered under suction. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water and recrystallised from least quantity of cold water, yield 7.5 g.

The compound is colorless and crystalline. It is moderately soluble in water, much less than the lanthanum dithionate itself which has been described as highly soluble by Cleve. It melts at about 260° with decomposition. Solubility at 35° = 6.58 g./100 c.c. [Found: La, 17.25, 17.46; S, 12.22, 12.18; N, 21.18, 21.18. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires La, 17.39; S, 12.01; N, 21.03 per cent].

Cerous ^{III}-urotropin dithionate was prepared in the same way, using cerous nitrate. Its properties resemble the other salt in many respects. It melts at about 262° with decomposition. Solubility at 35° = 5.02 g./100 c.c. [Found: Ce, 17.75, 17.68; S, 12.16, 12.32; N, 21.32, 21.15. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Ce, 17.5; S, 12.00; N, 21.0 per cent].

Praseodymium-urotropin dithionate was prepared similarly using praseodymium nitrate. The compound separates in beautiful green crystals. In other respects it resembles the corresponding lanthanum and cerium salts. Solubility at 35° = 3.35 g./100 c.c. [Found: Pr, 17.85, 17.67; S, 12.08, 12.18; N, 21.16, 21.02. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Pr, 17.60; S, 11.98; N, 20.97 per cent].

Lanthanum-hexa-antipyrene dithionate was similarly prepared from lanthanum nitrate, antipyrene and sodium dithionate. The compound separated in colorless beautiful crystals. Unlike the simple dithionate of lanthanum, the solubility of the complex is very low. It does not melt at any definite temperature and decomposes on heating. Solubility at 35° = 1.68 g./100 c.c. [Found: La, 14.88, 14.36; S, 10.36, 10.28; N, 9.12, 8.88. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires La, 14.74; S, 10.18; N, 8.91 per cent].

Cerous ^{III}-hexa-antipyrene Dithionate.—The method of preparation is identical as the previous compound. Solubility at 35° = 1.12 g./100 c.c. [Found: Ce, 15.02; S, 10.36; N, 8.86. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires Ce, 14.83; S, 10.17; N, 8.90 per cent].

Praseodymium-hexa-antipyrene dithionate was obtained in the same way as the cerous ^{III} complex. The salt separated as beautiful green shining crystals. Solubility at 35° = 0.94 g./100 c.c. [Found: Pr, 15.08; S, 10.42; N, 8.78. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires Pr, 14.92; S, 10.16; N, 8.89 per cent].

Method of Analysis.—Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate after oxidation with nitric acid and bromine and separation of rare earth from this solution with ammonia. Rare earth was estimated by dissolving this precipitate in hydrochloric acid and then reprecipitating as oxalate and subsequent ignition to oxide. Nitrogen, in urotropin compounds, was estimated after decomposition with concentrated sulphuric acid, and distillation with caustic soda, absorbing the evolved ammonia in standard acid, and titrating back the excess acid with standard alkali. Nitrogen, in antipyrene complexes, was determined by Duma's method of combustion.